

On the optimality of ternary arithmetic for compactness and hardware design[☆]

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Abstract

In this paper, the optimality of ternary arithmetic is investigated under strict mathematical formulation. The arithmetic systems are presented in generic form, as the means to encode numeric values, and the choice of radix is asserted as the main parameter to assess the efficiency of the representation, in terms of information compactness and estimated implementation cost in hardware. Using proper formulations for the optimization task, the universal constant e (base of natural logarithms) is proven as the most efficient radix and ternary is asserted as the closest integer choice.

Keywords: arithmetic systems, ternary arithmetic, computer technology

1. Introduction

The term *arithmetic system* refers to the way a number is represented as a sequence of symbols associated with a specific power series. More specifically, a *radix* r is selected as the base of the arithmetic system and every number is expressed as a sum of powers of this radix.

As humans, we learn to count in the *decimal* arithmetic system, i.e., using powers of 10, purely for practical reasons. Children learn basic arithmetic by using their ten fingers, thus each time they count to 10, a carrier is created and added to the next power index. For example, the number 1,234 is actually a shortcut to the full representation:

$$1234_{10} = 1 \cdot 1.000 + 2 \cdot 100 + 3 \cdot 10 + 4 = 1 \cdot 10^3 + 2 \cdot 10^2 + 3 \cdot 10^1 + 4 \cdot 10^0$$

The proper representation of the number orders the coefficients for each radix power in left-to-right ranking and includes a subscript displaying the radix. The

[☆]Some explanations and derivations in equations are presented in explicit detail, in order to be more readable as lecture material for undergraduate students.

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representation may include a sign, a fractional point and negative powers, in order to represent any real number:

$$-12.34_{10} = (-1) (1 \cdot 10^1 + 2 \cdot 10^0 + 3 \cdot 10^{-1} + 4 \cdot 10^{-2})$$

Any radix may be used instead of 10 to represent the same number in different arithmetic systems. The general formula for representing $x \in \mathbf{R}$ is:

$$x = \dots + c_2 \cdot r^2 + c_1 \cdot r^1 + c_0 \cdot r^0 + c_{-1} \cdot r^{-1} + \dots = \sum_{k=-m}^n c_k \cdot r^k \quad (1)$$

where r is the radix used, k are the power indices and c_k are appropriate coefficients to represent a given number x (sign is omitted here). It is clear that for a specified positive radix, the corresponding representation for x is unique. Theoretically, both the coefficients and the radix use can be negative and/or non-integers, although this may complicate the representation. On the other hand, choosing the proper radix can result in more efficient and *compact* representation. For example, $1024_{10} = 1 \cdot 2^{10} = 1000000000_2$ but also $1024_{10} = 1 \cdot 1024^1 = 10_{1024}$ and all three representations can be used equivalently.

In every arithmetic system, the radix r determines the valid range for the c_k coefficients, since these are upper-bounded in every power position by the next one, and for each valid value a unique symbol is required. Hence, in the decimal system the valid symbols are $\{0, \dots, 9\}$, in the binary system these are $\{0, 1\}$, in the hexadecimal these are $\{0, \dots, 9, A, \dots, F\}$, etc. In general, if the radix is chosen as a positive integer $r > 1$ and $c_k \geq 0$ then the valid range is $0 \leq c_k \leq r - 1$, since when $c_k = r$ then it results in carrier $c_{k+1} = 1$ and $c_k = 0$.

From these basic common properties of all arithmetic systems it is clear that using a large radix results in more compact representation, but a larger set of symbols is required. In contrast, using a small radix results in longer representation, but a smaller set of symbols. This can be easily verified with arithmetic systems where the radix of one is a multiplication of the other, for example $255_{10} = 11111111_2 = FF_{16}$.

2. Problem definition

The problem of defining an optimal arithmetic representation has been around for many decades, especially in the very early years of computing technologies. In particular, mathematicians and engineers have been trying to propose the best arithmetic system that would be used as the basis for computers back in the '50s and '60s [1].

The earliest published discussion on this subject is probably in the 1950 book by U.S. Navy and Engineering Research Associates [2]. In particular, the product of the radix and the size of the symbols set was considered a good predictor of the cost of the hardware (electronic components) required to build digital computers. In particular, the best radix for optimal arithmetic and

compact number representation was calculated close to 3, thus producing the notion of a *ternary* system.

Before this assertion is formally proven, one more comment should be noted with regard to integer power series and their summations. In Eq.1 the coefficients c_k can take any value in the valid range $0 \leq c_k \leq r - 1$. Without loss of generality, we limit the problem to positive integers, hence the maximum number that can be represented with a fixed width $w + 1$ is when $c_k = r - 1$, $\forall k = \{0, \dots, w\}$. The +1 is for the zero-index power r^0 . Hence, we can now calculate the maximum number that can be represented with $w + 1$ symbols (size) in an arithmetic system of radix r as follows:

Theorem 1. *The maximum number U that can be represented with $w + 1$ symbols (size) in an arithmetic system of radix $r > 1$ is upper-bounded by r^{w+1} .*

Proof. Using Eq.1 and setting $c_k = r - 1$, $\forall k = \{0, \dots, w\}$, it results to:

$$U = \sum_{k=0}^w (r - 1) r^k = \sum_{k=0}^w r^{k+1} - \sum_{k=0}^w r^k = r^{w+1} + (1 - 1) \sum_{k=1}^w r^{k+1} + r^0 = r^{w+1} - 1 \quad (2)$$

□

It should be noted that the result in Eq.2 is compatible with the sum of a geometric series [3] via:

$$\sum_{k=1}^n a^k = \frac{a^{n+1} - 1}{a - 1} \quad (3)$$

and thus:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=0}^w (r - 1) r^k &= \sum_{k=0}^w r^{k+1} - \sum_{k=0}^w r^k \\ &= \frac{r^{w+2} - 1}{r - 1} - 1 - \frac{r^{w+1} - 1}{r - 1} \\ &= \frac{r^{w+1}(r - 1)}{r - 1} - \frac{r - 1}{r - 1} = r^{w+1} - 1 \end{aligned}$$

According to Eq.2, the maximum number that can be represented with $w + 1$ symbols (set size) in an arithmetic system of radix r is upper-bounded by r^{w+1} . This result from Theorem 1 is very useful indeed, since it is valid for any radix r . For example, the maximum four-digit decimal number is ($w = 3$): $9999_{10} = 10000_{10} - 1 = 10^4 - 1$.

3. Formalizations and proofs

In the previous section the problem was clearly defined: *Given that the radix and the size of number representation in any arithmetic system are inversely associated, how can we choose the “best” combination?*

Figure 1: A sample packed tree organization for exactly 39 items.

To understand the nature of this problem and the way to solve it, a number can be viewed as a collection of distinct items, a set with size that corresponds to this value. This collection can then be organized in the form of a tree, with nodes of equal size and depth appropriate to completely accommodate this set. Such an example for the number 39 is presented in Figure 1.

In Figure 1 each node contains exactly three items and each one of them is the root for three similar sub-trees. The tree presented is filled completely and no more items can be added without expanding it to greater depth. In other words, there are 39 items filling the entire tree up to a depth of three, thus the tree is *packed* and no representation more compact than this can be created, considering this specific node size and sub-trees structure.

It is easy to see that depth d contains m^d items: $m^1 = 3$, $m^2 = 3 \cdot 3 = 9$ and $m^3 = 3 \cdot 3 \cdot 3 = 27$. Hence, the sum of all the items in the tree is: $3+9+27=39$. Not surprisingly, this is exactly what Eq.3 gives when $a = 3$ and $n = 3$:

$$\sum_{k=1}^3 3^k = \frac{3^{3+1} - 1}{3 - 1} = \frac{81 - 1}{2} = 40$$

where the sum 40 includes the zero-power item or “root” of the tree of Figure 1 (not shown). In other words, if the upper bound that is asserted by Theorem 1 is considered as the size of a collection of distinct items, then radix r and width w are associated with the node size m and the required depth d , respectively, if a packed tree organization is employed. In this case, the tree depth d , therefore the width w too, can be estimated by employing Eq.3 and using the base- m logarithm:

$$40 = \frac{3^{d+1} - 1}{3 - 1} \Rightarrow 3^{d+1} = 40 \cdot 2 + 1 \Rightarrow d + 1 = \log_3 81 = 4$$

or in a more general form, using Eq.3:

$$a^{n+1} = 1 + (a - 1) \sum_{k=1}^n a^k \Rightarrow d = \log_a \left(1 + (a - 1) \sum_{k=1}^n a^k \right) - 1 \quad (4)$$

What Eq.4 tells us is that the (minimum) depth of such a packed tree is directly related to the node size. Considering this tree organization as a metaphor for the upper bound $U = r^{w+1} - 1$ that is asserted by Theorem 1, the width w can be calculated in a similar way as in Eq.4:

$$U = r^{w+1} - 1 \Rightarrow (w + 1) \log_r r = \log_r (U + 1) \Rightarrow w = \log_r (U + 1) - 1 \quad (5)$$

For example, the number $U = 255_{10}$ represented with $r = 2$ (binary) requires: $w = \log_2 (256) - 1 = 7$. This is exactly what Theorem 1 states, with $w + 1 = 8$ coefficients for the power indices $\{2^7, \dots, 2^0\}$ and $U = 1111111_2 = 255_{10}$.

Using the tree structure metaphor and the problem formalization presented above as an optimization task, the following theorem describes the solution for the “best” arithmetic system in terms of information packing and representation efficiency:

Theorem 2. *Under the minimization criterion $E_1(r, w) = r \cdot w$ and subject to $r^w = C \neq 0$ (constant), where $r > 1$ is the radix and $w \in [0, r - 1]$, the optimal information packing for number representation is achieved for an arithmetic system with: $r = e$, the base of the natural logarithm ($e = 2.718, 281, 828, 459\dots$).*

Proof. The goal is to minimize: $E_1(r, w) = r \cdot w$, s.t. $r^w = C \neq 0$ (constant). Since $r > 1$, from the constraint we have:

$$r^w = C \Leftrightarrow w \cdot \log_a r = \log_a C \Leftrightarrow w = \frac{\log_a C}{\log_a r} \quad (6)$$

Therefore, substituting Eq.6 in the minimization criterion, then taking the first derivative [3] and calculating for root(s), gives:

$$\frac{\partial (E_1(r, w))}{\partial r} = 0 \Rightarrow \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \cdot \frac{\log_a C}{\log_a r} \right) = \log_a C \left(\frac{\frac{\partial r}{\partial r} \cdot \log_a r - r \cdot \frac{\partial \log_a r}{\partial r}}{\log_a^2 r} \right) = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{\ln C}{\ln a} \left(\frac{\frac{\ln r}{\ln a} - \frac{r}{r \cdot \ln a}}{\left(\frac{\ln r}{\ln a} \right)^2} \right) = \frac{\ln C}{\ln a} \left(\frac{\frac{1}{\ln a} (\ln r - 1)}{\frac{1}{\ln a} \cdot \frac{\ln^2 r}{\ln a}} \right) = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\Rightarrow \ln C \left(\frac{1}{\ln r} - \frac{1}{\ln^2 r} \right) = \frac{\ln C}{\ln r} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\ln r} \right) = 0 \quad (8)$$

From Eq.7 it becomes clear that the calculation will eventually reduce to the simple: $\ln r - 1 = 0$. It is worth noting that in Eq.8 there is no reference to a , i.e., the base of the logarithm used in Eq.6 is indeed irrelevant, as expected. From here, the derivation of the root is straight-forward:

Figure 2: Plot of the $E_1(r, w)$ cost function ($\ln C = 1$) and the optimal solution at $r = e$.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial (E_1(r, w))}{\partial r} = 0 &\Rightarrow \frac{\ln C}{\ln r} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\ln r}\right) = 0 \\ &\Rightarrow \ln r = 1 \Rightarrow e^{\ln r} = e^1 \Rightarrow r = e \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

□

Figure 2 illustrates the plot of $E_1(r, w)$ cost function (using $\ln(\cdot)$ and $\ln C = 1$) against radix r and the optimal solution at $r = e$. This is the representation “cost” measured as the product of node size and tree depth, i.e., analogous to the 2-D “size” of the associated tree, if a specific number (upper bound) C is treated as a collection of distinct items. The shape of the function makes it clear that there is a well-defined and unique minimum, at the point where the radix is equal to the base of the natural logarithm. It is very important to point out that, under this very generic formalization of the problem, the optimal solution is independent to both the actual upper bound C , as well as the base of the logarithm used in the proof.

The question now becomes: *How generic is this assertion?* In other words, can we use some other optimality criterion and derive some other solution for the “best” radix?

In order to investigate this, we can try and formulate an alternative cost function and work in a similar way. Although the tree structure metaphor leads naturally to a product between radix r and width w , the sum of these two parameters may be used as an alternative test case. Theorem 3 exploits this possibility with $E_2(r, w)$ and states the corresponding solution(s):

Theorem 3. *Under the minimization criterion $E_2(r, w) = r + w$ and subject to $r^w = C \neq 0$ (constant), where $r > 1$ is the radix and $w \in [0, r - 1]$, the optimal information packing for number representation is achieved for an arithmetic system with r equal to the root(s) of: $f(r) = r \cdot \ln^2 r - \ln C = 0$ (C -dependent).*

Proof. The goal is to minimize: $E_2(r, w) = r + w$, s.t. $r^w = C \neq 0$ (constant). Again, since $r > 1$, from the constraint we have Eq.6. Substituting in the minimization criterion, then taking the first derivative [3] and calculating for root(s), gives:

$$\frac{\partial(E_2(r, w))}{\partial r} = 0 \Rightarrow \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r + \frac{\log_a C}{\log_a r} \right) = 1 + \log_a C \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{1}{\log_a r} \right) = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow 1 + \ln C \cdot \frac{\partial(\ln^{-1} r)}{\partial r} = 1 - \frac{\ln C}{\ln^2 r} \cdot \frac{\partial \ln r}{\partial r} = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$\Rightarrow 1 - \frac{\ln C}{r \cdot \ln^2 r} = 0 \Rightarrow r \cdot \ln^2 r = \ln C \quad (11)$$

□

From Eq.10 it becomes clear that the constant term $\ln C$ will not be removed from the final calculation, which is confirmed in Eq.11. As before, it is worth noting that in Eq.11 there is no reference to a , i.e., the base of the logarithm used in Eq.6 is indeed irrelevant.

Figure 3 illustrates the plot of the first derivative $\frac{\partial E_2(r, w)}{\partial r}$ of the cost function against radix r . From Eq.11 it is evident that the curve is C -dependent, therefore the minimization solutions are too. The plot shows the corresponding curves for various values of C and Table 1 shows the exact solutions of the associated minimization. Again, the solution is independent to the base of the logarithm used in the proof, but *dependent* to the actual upper bound C . Therefore, this choice of cost function does not lead to a generic solution, although the partial solutions remain asymptotically close to four.

4. Discussion

As stated earlier, the formalization of the cost function $E_1(r, w) = r \cdot w$ in Theorem 2 is compatible with the tree organization metaphor of number

Figure 3: Plot of the $\frac{\partial E_2(r,w)}{\partial r}$ cost function, which is actually C -dependent.

Table 1: Sample solutions to $\frac{\partial E_2(r,w)}{\partial r} = 0$ for various values of C .

C	r
e	1.4215
10	2.5746
50	3.0841
200	3.4519
500	3.6724
1000	3.8303

representation in any arithmetic system. It is also the actual cost estimator that was employed in the early years of computing back in the '50s and '60s to predict the hardware cost of implementing such electronic processing and memory systems [2]. The ternary arithmetic, not the binary, seemed to be the right choice for the computers of the next decades.

Indeed, the first ternary-arithmetic computer² was built at Moscow State University during the race of the Cold War by Nikolai P. Brusentsov and his colleagues [1, 4]. It was named “Setun” and 50 such machines were built between 1958 and 1965. It operated with arithmetic units of 18 ternary digits or *trits* (instead of *bits*), producing a numerical range of $3^{18} = 387,420,489$ integer numbers. In contrast, according to Eq.6 a modern binary computer requires $18 \cdot \frac{\ln 3}{\ln 2} = 28.529\dots < 29$ bits to represent the same range. However, there were no three-state electronics circuitry at the time and the machines were built using two pairs of magnetic cores, i.e., inherently a four-state device to implement ternary arithmetic. Obviously, this approach produces hardware that is 25% less efficient than pure binary and, as a result, the Setun project was far from success.

Nevertheless, the ternary approach seemed to have many advantages, not only in relation to information packing in memory circuitry but also in terms of robust flow control in programs (e.g. three-way ordering/logic comparisons in a single step). In the '60s several test projects were developed for ternary logic gates and memory cells for building more and more complex digital units, such as adders and multiplexers. In 1973 Gideon Frieder and his colleagues at the State University of New York designed and implemented (in Fortran) a software emulator for “Ternac” [5], a ternary computer similar to Setun.

Donald E. Knuth, one of the founders of modern programming and Informatics in general, has wrote in his seminal book “The Art of Computer Programming” (1968) [6, 7] that ternary arithmetic is “...*perhaps the prettiest number system of all...*”, explaining the numerous advantages over binary or any other system. Despite the theoretical arguments, the ternary approach never made it to mainstream computer manufacturing, mostly due to the advent of cheap solid-state circuitry of binary logic that revolutionized the digital technology of the 20th century.

In the last two decades or so, quantum computing [8] seems to finally get into solid foundations and hardware implementations, although it is still constrained to only few *qubits*. One of the main advantages of the quantum approach to computing is the inherent multi-valued logic that can be implemented directly in single memory cells and logic gates [9, 10]. Obviously, ternary is a serious candidate as the base of quantum arithmetic, if the implementation cost of each qubit continues to be even loosely relevant to the arguments presented here.

²Actually, one early ternary machine was built entirely from wood by Thomas Fowler in 1840 and it operated in balanced ternary [4].

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